

A MAJOR DISTRACTIVE AND DESTRUCTIVE FACTOR OR A HELPFUL TOOL?

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Abstract

Social media can encourage casual conversations between colleagues and help build healthy workplace relationships. It is the easiest and quickest way to encourage employees to interact with their co-workers even after work.

A growing hot topic, and cause for concern is the increasing use of social media in the workplace. The landscape for communication has changed, and the line between personal and professional communications has been blurred. How will your employer manage the risks associated with the use of social media and at the same time, gain the benefits that this media form provides? While many employers were initially concerned that employees would use company time and equipment for socializing with friends, they are quickly learning that many social networks can also be used directly for work purposes.

When that technology is used to view, collect or disseminate inappropriate content, again employers have cause for concern. Use of workplace computers with social media has become an offence many corporate doesn't allow people to use social media in their entity or zone and few give them a different zone altogether to use social media on timely breaks frequently results in discipline and workplace harassment complaints. In some cases it can even result in serious criminal investigations.

There are pros and Cons of my study which gives us an idea in today's world we are alone but with electrical gadgets we are socially not alone.

Key words- *Casual Conversation, disseminate, inappropriate, criminal investigations*

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Introduction-

When employees interact with individuals outside the organization, they are less motivated and

show less initiative. These findings suggest that the effects of social media depend on who employees interact with; employees who interact with their colleagues share meaningful work experiences, but those making connections outside the organization are distracted and unproductive.

Pros of social media in the workplace

1. Allows employees to take a much-needed mental break

According to a survey, the major reason why most employees use social media at work is to take a mental health break from all the stress of their job. Social media gives people an escape into the digital world. It allows them to view anything they want to, without having to walk outside their office or go to the break room.

2. Improves employee engagement

Giving social media access to employees on their work devices strengthens their confidence, makes them feel valued, boosts their mood, and increases employee engagement. When employees recognize that their employers have confidence in them, it directly translates into better work as employees feel more responsible and accountable for the work that they do and the amount of time that they spend on social media.

3. Strengthens team bonding and workplace relationships

Social media can encourage casual conversations between colleagues and help build healthy workplace relationships. It is the easiest and quickest way to encourage employees to interact with their coworkers even after work. Since it is a more natural way of building connections, it can help improve camaraderie and team bonding in the organization.

Cons of social media in the workplace

1. Decreases productivity

Too much of everything can be dangerous, and that includes social media as well. On average, people spend approximately 2 hours and 23 minutes ^[3] on social media every day. If your employees spend even half of that time scrolling through social media platforms during work hours, it can affect their productivity immensely. There is so much content available on social media with new content being uploaded every second, its way too easy to fall down the spiral and get addicted.

2. Social media fails

Social media can both make and break your reputation. Irresponsible posts or comments can quickly go viral and create public outrage. There have been many instances before where people were fired from their jobs for being rude, degrading, and insulting on social media which can also bring a lot of heat on the company itself.

3. Causes jealousy among employees

People tend to post a lot of personal stuff on social media — New car, new house, a new piece of jewellery, or a big vacation. Seeing their colleagues enjoy all these things in life can make people jealous which can, in turn, drag down employee morale, team bonding, and directly affect the team's efficiency.

How social media affects productivity and mindset of employees

Social media influences all of our lives as we spend a disproportionate amount of time on it. While social media was built with the aim to help people connect and share their views, now it is all about people creating and consuming content at a tremendous rate. There is always a new hashtag, a new outrage, and a new debate waiting for you every time you open it.

Findings

In the First part of my study I have surveyed the employees about why and how they use platforms like Facebook, Twitter or LinkedIn Respondents were asked about their behaviours including whether they felt motivated in their jobs & showed initiative at work. I found that employees who engage in online social interactions with co-workers through social media blogs tend to be more motivated and come up with innovative ideas.

In the second part of the study I found that employees using social media were more likely to leave an organization. This may be because they were more likely to engage with potential new employers than their less social peers. In my study, 76% of employees using social media for work took an interest in other organizations they found on social media, compared to 60% of employees using social media only for leisure. When I examined how respondents expressed openness to new careers and employers, I found that they engaged in some key activities including researching new organizations and making new work connections. The chart below shows how respondents from both groups those who used social media at work

Electronic International Interdisciplinary Research Journal

Volume-XI, Issues-I

Jan - Feb 2022

and those who didn't engaged in these activities

These findings present a conundrum for managers: employees using social media at work are more engaged and more productive, but they are also more likely to leave your company. Managers can address this problem in two ways. First, managers should implement solutions that neutralize the retention risk caused by social media. They can leverage social media training to make employees focus on positive social media behaviours, like collaboration, which can increase satisfaction and attachment, countering turnover risks.

Second, managers can turn the threat into an opportunity. Managers can create social media groups in which employees will be more likely to collaborate and less likely to share withdrawal intentions or discussions about external job opportunities. Managers can use social media to directly reduce turnover intentions, by recognizing employees' accomplishments and giving visibility to employees' success stories. This approach has the added benefit of serving as a recruiting tool: If, on one side, the use of social media can make your employees leave the organization, on the other side, the same use of social media from employees of other organizations could attract them to your organization.

Conclusion

Accordingly to study employees that use social media to interact with their colleagues tend to be more motivated and they often come up with innovative ideas at work. On the other hand, when employees interact with individuals outside their company, they tend to become less motivated and show less initiative at work. This study clearly suggests that the impact and effect of social media on employees really depends on who they interact with. Employees who interact directly with their colleagues are able to share and create meaningful work experiences, but those that make connections with professionals outside their organizations are unproductive and distracted at work.

Finding a healthy alternative for social media for employees and teams

It's clear that organizations need some way to encourage casual conversations among their employees but giving access to complete social media cannot just hamper productivity but it can also decrease employee engagement and retention.

It's good for employees to stay connected online, but they should also be focused when it comes to work. Social media platforms can only be a temporary solution for companies to

encourage employees to interact with their colleagues and share their thoughts online. If you don't switch to a healthy alternative soon, you will start seeing the negative effects of social media in your organization which will invariably affect efficiency and team bonding. That is why organizations should focus more on social collaboration instead of giving uninterrupted access to social media platforms.

A healthy alternative that encourages social collaboration is a digital workplace platform that allows employees to network and collaborate easily. The biggest benefits of digital workplace are that it doesn't give access to anyone outside the organization. By giving you the access controls, it lets you decide who should have access to which parts of the platform.

With a digital workplace, employees can share their opinions and discuss important projects without any privacy issues since the platform is only accessible by employees within the company. It's also possible to create private communication channels within the digital workplace to keep conversations restricted to your team only in case you are working on a confidential project.

With a single place to manage all their work tasks, documents, and conversations, employees will no longer be overwhelmed with multiple applications and it becomes easier for them to have contextual conversations. More importantly, employees don't get distracted by random viral posts online or the latest online outrage which can help them focus better at work. A digital workplace gives employees all the benefits of social media but by limiting it to the organization, it helps avoid all the disadvantages and distractions for traditional social media. In my research i came across a new digital platform known as Kissflow :-

Kissflow: A digital workplace platform that nurtures social collaboration Kissflow is a digital workplace platform that makes social collaboration easier by giving employees a centralized platform to collaborate, communicate, and manage their everyday work. It offers project management, centralized cloud storage, knowledge repository, as well as private and public communication channels.

Data Analysis and Interpretation

Count of 2. Use Social Media to find out about other organizations

Count of 7. Is social media distracting you from your work?

Count of 3. Use Social Media to make New

Count of 6. Find Social Media a helpful tool

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